

Supplementary material

Gaussian or Gamma distribution: **fixed** variance or **variable** variance

	Vastus medialis	Tibialis Anterior	Medial Gastrocnemius
MEP (μ Vs)	Gamma:variable	Gamma:fixed	Gamma:fixed
sEMR (μ Vs)		Gamma:fixed	Gamma:variable
sEMR %M _{max}	Gamma:fixed		
MEP latency (ms)	Gamma:fixed	Gamma:fixed	Gaussian:fixed
sEMR latency (ms)	Gaussian:fixed	Gamma:fixed	Gamma:fixed
Doublet ratio (%)	Gaussian:variable	Gaussian:fixed	Gaussian:variable
M _{max} (μ Vs)	Gamma:fixed		
M _{max} latency (ms)	Gaussian:variable		
sEMR – Mwave latency (ms)	Gamma:fixed		
The distribution (Gaussian or Gamma) and variance (fixed or variable) chosen for each outcome measure.			

Additional results

For VM M_{max} area there was no effect of intensity ($\chi^2(1) = 0.153$, $p = 0.696$), waveform ($\chi^2(1) = 0.135$, $p = 0.713$), nor an intensity by waveform interaction ($\chi^2(1) = 0.204$, $p = 0.652$).

M_{max} latency showed no effect of intensity ($\chi^2(1) = 0.867$, $p = 0.352$), or waveform ($\chi^2(1) = 2.943$, $p = 0.086$) but an intensity by waveform interaction ($\chi^2(1) = 6.709$, $p = 0.010$; GLMM), however no planned contrasts were significant ($p > 0.094$).

For the VM MEP area, there was no effect of intensity ($\chi^2(1) = 0.11$, $p = 0.74$), waveform ($\chi^2(1) = 0.255$, $p = 0.613$), nor an intensity by waveform interaction ($\chi^2(1) < 0.001$, $p = 0.995$).

For VM MEP latency there was no effect of intensity ($\chi^2(1) = 0.372$, $p = 0.542$), waveform ($\chi^2(1) = 0.004$, $p = 0.95$), or intensity by waveform interaction ($\chi^2(1) = 0.035$, $p = 0.852$).

TA MEP areas showed no effect of intensity ($\chi^2(1) = 0.476$, $p = 0.49$), waveform ($\chi^2(1) = 0.129$, $p = 0.719$), or intensity by waveform interaction ($\chi^2(1) = 0.362$, $p = 0.548$).

TA MEP latencies were similar across conditions with no effect of intensity ($\chi^2(1) = 2.398$, $p = 0.121$), waveform ($\chi^2(1) < 0.001$, $p = 0.985$) or intensity by waveform ($\chi^2(1) = 0.88$, $p = 0.348$).

MG MEP areas showed no effect of intensity ($\chi^2(1) = 1.583$, $p = 0.208$), or waveform ($\chi^2(1) = 1.625$, $p = 0.202$) but an intensity by waveform interaction ($\chi^2(1) = 3.918$, $p = 0.048$). No differences were found for our planned contrasts ($p > 0.63$).

MG MEP latencies were similar across conditions with no effect of intensity ($\chi^2(1) = 0.407$, $p = 0.523$), waveform ($\chi^2(1) = 0.002$, $p = 0.966$) or interaction ($\chi^2(1) = 0.776$, $p = 0.378$).